

EFFECT OF AUDIT COMMITTEE CHARACTERISTICS ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA

JOHN ADAMU¹, OFILI UGWUDIOHA² and KOLAWOLE EBIRE³

^{1,2}Department of Accounting, Nile University of Nigeria.

³Department of Banking and Finance, Nile University of Nigeria.

Abstract

In contemporary accounting, audit committees have gained significant prominence as a critical component in ensuring transparency, accountability, and financial integrity within organizations. As such, the effectiveness of audit committees has become a subject of increasing interest, particularly in the context of their influence on financial performance. This study therefore examined the effect of audit committee characteristics on financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2012 to 2022. The proxy for audit committee characteristics is audit committee size, audit committee independence, audit committee frequency of meetings, audit committee financial expertise and audit committee board gender diversity. Financial performance was proxy using Return on Asset (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). The control variable used in the study is firm size which was proxy as total asset. The study used secondary panel data which were sourced from the audited annual report of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. A sample of 47 firms was used in the study. The null hypotheses were tested using fixed random effect which was determined by the Hausman test. The findings showed that Audit committee size has an insignificant positive effect on financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee independence has an insignificant positive effect on financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee frequency of meetings has an insignificant negative effect on financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee financial expertise has a significant positive effect on ROA. In contrast, the result is insignificant and negative on ROE of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee gender diversity has a significant negative effect on financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on this, the study recommends that manufacturing enterprises should prioritize financial skills across the organization. This encompasses the finance department, management staff, and board of directors. Improving key personnel's financial acumen and talents will result in more accurate financial reporting, better financial decision-making, and overall financial performance.

Keywords: Audit Committee Independence, Audit Committee Financial Expertise, Audit Committee Board Gender Diversity, ROA, ROE.

1. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary corporate governance, audit committees have gained significant prominence as a critical component in ensuring transparency, accountability, and financial integrity within organizations.

As such, the effectiveness of audit committees has become a subject of increasing interest, particularly in the context of their influence on financial performance. This study delves into the nuanced relationship between audit committee characteristics and financial performance, specifically focusing on manufacturing firms.

There is a consensus that female representation on the board improves the quality of governance as they increase the intensity of monitoring and are more independent. For example, studies such as Shukla et al. (2021) and Dwalikat et al. (2021) found that women on the board influence financial performance. In contrast, Abubakar et al. (2023), Suherman et al. (2021) and Marashdeh et al. (2021), Ugbah et al. (2023), revealed that women directors do not have a significant effect on financial performance. Hence, the findings on the effect of board gender diversity and financial performance are inconclusive.

Hamada and Jwailes (2021) argued that firms with competent audit committees are more likely to have a lower probability of experiencing major accounting scandals, thereby lowering the chance of having unexpectedly poor firm performance.

Although the findings of previous studies on this association are inconclusive, an audit committee composed of non-executive directors does act better than a less independent committee since the former is more likely to provide better monitoring through its ability to resist pressure from managers.

Prior studies (Mawardi et al. 2023; Bazhair, 2022; Azam & Wang, 2021) on financial expertise and financial performance were conducted outside Nigeria and these findings cannot be generalized to Nigerian manufacturing firms. Hence, the current study will focus on Nigeria.

Prior empirical studies on audit committee characteristics and performance focused on different sectors such as non-financial firms (Abubakar et al. (2023), Bazhair, 2022; Al-Jalahma, 2022; El'Hawary, 2021; Orjinta & Ikueze, 2018, Tawfeeq & Alabdullah, 2023; Udoh, et al. (2023), Ugbah et al. 2023). Other studies concentrated on banks (Adewinmisi, et al. 2023, Fariha, et al., 2021; Okolie & Ogbaragu, 2022; Wobo & Ibanichuka, 2021; Olayinka, 2019).

Studies such as Daniel et al. (2021) were limited to consumer goods while Okeke (2023) was limited to insurance firms in Nigeria. Studies on manufacturing firms (such as Okeke, 2021; Ashari & Krismiaji, 2019; Maina & Oluoch, 2018; Ojeka et al. 2014) on audit committee characteristics on the financial performance were limited in scope to the period ended 2014 and 2018. The current study fills these gaps by extending the frontier of knowledge beyond 2018 to 2022 and using Return on Assets (ROA) as a measure of financial performance.

Given the above-mentioned gaps, it is important to determine how audit committee characteristics can contribute to financial performance. Many studies have underscored the importance of the size of the audit committee, composition, frequency of meetings, financial expertise, and gender diversity on firms' performance. However, the inconclusive findings on the audit committee's characteristics on financial performance call for further study.

In addition, the focus of previous studies on non-financial sectors leaves a gap that should be filled. Studies conducted in Nigeria had period gaps and used other financial performance measures. Furthermore, prior studies concentrated on other countries, which cannot be generalized to the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Hence, the current study explores this gap by examining the effect of audit committee characteristics on financial performance in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

In line with the objectives, the following hypotheses are stated in their null form:

- H₀₁: Audit committee size has no significant effect on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₂: Audit committee independence has no significant effect on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₃: Audit committee frequency of meetings has no significant effect on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₄: Audit committee financial expertise Audit committee frequency of meetings has no significant effect on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
- H₀₅: Audit committee gender diversity has no significant effect on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

An audit committee is a group of non-executive directors in the organization, according to Al-Thuneibut (2006). Given that most audit committees include both executive and non-executive members, this definition might be flawed because it solely includes non-executive directors. Similarly, an audit committee is described by Arens et al. (2009) as a group of individuals chosen from the board of directors who oversee providing oversight mechanisms for the company's internal control system. They went on to say that the main goal of setting up an audit committee is to raise the standard of financial reporting by strengthening the audits and monitoring the board of directors. Who should make up the committee was not covered by this study. The Nigerian code of corporate governance (2018) defines an audit committee as the committee responsible for audit, which public companies are required to constitute by extant laws. The code of corporate governance stipulates the characteristics that should be inherent among the committee members. This includes roles, compositions, size, and frequency of meetings. This study aligns with the Nigerian code of corporate governance (2018) definition and measures audit characteristics as audit committee size, audit committee independence, audit committee meetings, audit committee financial expertise and audit committee gender diversity.

The concept of firm financial performance implies measuring the results of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms. According to Daniel et al. (2021), financial performance measures how a firm uses its assets to run business activities to earn revenues. It examines the overall financial health of a business over a given period. Financial statements are the primary source of information for determining financial performance. They include the statement of financial position, which shows a company's assets, liabilities, and equity, the income statement, which shows revenues, expenses, and profits over time, the cash flow statement, which shows the sources and uses of cash over time, and the statement of changes in owners' equity, which shows changes in owner's equity over time. Rahel and Serkalem (2010) opined

that financial performance, which measures profitability and market value, is considered an indicator of how well the firm satisfies its owners and shareholders. The goal of firms is to increase their financial performance, particularly for public firms, in terms of shareholder value. Moreover, performance measurement systems aim to provide operational control and to provide external financial reporting. This study proxy financial performance as Return on Asset (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

Theoretical Review

This study is underpinned by the Agency theory by Jensen and Meckling (1976). The study's adoption of the agency theory and the tokenism theory is based on its research objectives. Specifically, it aims to reduce agency conflicts in the composition of the board of directors in order to maximize shareholder wealth. Additionally, it explains board diversity in relation to corporations and how it impacts the corporation's performance. The idea goes on to describe how having a diverse board can create the right kind of equilibrium to improve an employee's social assets, which in turn will improve the worker's performance and happiness and ultimately the performance of the company. According to the tenets of the agency theory, managers are frequently motivated to act against the interests of shareholders and in their own best interests when there is a conflict between them and the shareholders, particularly when opportunistic behavior is involved (Jensen & Meckling 1976). Because managers are more prone to stray from safeguarding the interests of shareholders in the absence of adequate market laws and monitoring instruments, the agency theory is pertinent to this study. Therefore, the main goal of sound corporate governance procedures like an audit committee is to lessen these kinds of conflicts.

Juwita (2023) used audit fees as a moderating variable to examine how gender diversity on the board of directors, board of commissioners, and audit committee affects the quality of financial statements from 2019 to 2021. The panel regression analysis demonstrates that gender and women play a key role in the Corporate Governance process. The focus of this study was limited to Indonesia which does not apply to Nigeria. Musah et al. (2022) examined the effect of board characteristics, audit committee characteristics, and gender diversity on audit fees of listed firms in Ghana. Panel regression. The study also shows that female representation on board and other top-level positions among listed firms is low. The results of the regression analysis show that female representation on the board had a negative relationship with audit fees. The findings of this study were limited to Ghana. Also, the present study deviates from this study by focusing on gender diversity and financial performance.

Shukla et al. (2021) investigated the effect of board gender diversity on the financial performance of 29 Indian banks from 2009 to 2016. The secondary data were analysed using panel regression. The study concluded that women on boards influenced financial performance. The findings of the study are limited to Indian banks while the current study focus on manufacturing. Suherman et al. (2021) examined the impact of women directors on the financial performance of 264 non-financial corporations in Indonesia from 2013 to 2017. The panel data were extracted from the annual reports of the sampled corporation. The findings revealed that women directors do not have a significant effect on financial performance. The

current study focus on manufacturing firms. Dwalikat et al. (2021) used a two-stage least squares method to assess the effect of women on the board of directors on the financial performance of non-financial companies in Palestine from 2008 to 2015. The secondary data were analysed using panel regression. The findings showed that women on the board of directors are positively significant to financial performance. The study is limited to non-financial companies quoted in Palestine.

Abubakar et al. (2023) assessed whether board and audit effectiveness reduce financial constraint of the non-financial firms in Nigeria. The KZ index was used to measure financial constraint, and gender diversity and independence of the audit committee were adopted as determinants of effectiveness of the board and audit. Using data extracted from the annual reports of all the 87 listed non-financial firms in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), the analysis was done by running the descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression. The results of the analysis show that gender diversity has a negative and significant effect on financial constraint. This study therefore concludes that gender diversity helps save firms from financial constraint problems. This simply imply that that while high gender diversity on the boards of directors reduces financial constraint of firms, independence of the audit committee does not mitigate financial constraint situation of firms in Nigeria.

Onyekwere and Babangida (2022) examined 12 commercial banks in Nigeria for 2015 through 2019. The secondary data were analyzed using panel regression analysis. Findings showed a positive significant effect of female directors on firm financial performance. The current study will extend the scope to manufacturing firms. Awotomilusi and Dare (2022) investigated the influence of gender diversity on the firm value of Nigeria's listed DMBs from 2011 to 2020. Panel regression results revealed that female board audit committee had a statistically insignificant negative effect on firm value. The current study extends the scope to manufacturing firms. Kabara et al. (2022) examined how board diversity in terms of the gender and educational level of directors affects the performance of non-financial firms on the Nigerian stock exchange companies from 2012 to 2019. Using GMM, the findings support the existence of a significant positive influence of gender diversity on the companies' performance. The study focused on non-financial firms while the current study focused on manufacturing firms.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts ex post facto research design to examine the effect of audit committee characteristics on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The source of data for this study is from secondary sources, which will be extracted from the annual financial statements of the listed manufacturing firms for the period 2012 to 2022. The secondary source is more appropriate because all information needed for the study is available in the manufacturing firms' financial statements. The data extracted include audit committee gender diversity, audit committee size, audit committee independence, audit committee frequency of meetings, audit committee financial expertise and ROA. The population consist of all listed manufacturing firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2022.

The total number of manufacturing firms listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 2022 were 52.

Model Specification and Variable Measurement

The panel regression model that captures the effects of audit committee characteristics on financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is presented below:

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 ACS_{it} + \beta_2 ACI_{it} + \beta_3 ACM_{it} + \beta_4 ACFE_{it} + \beta_5 ACGD_{it} + \beta_6 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$ROE_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 ACS_{it} + \beta_2 ACI_{it} + \beta_3 ACM_{it} + \beta_4 ACFE_{it} + \beta_5 ACGD_{it} + \beta_6 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Table 1: Description of Variables

Variables	Type	Description	Source
ROA	Dependent variable	Measured as net income divided by total assets	Udoh et al. (2023)
ROE	Dependent Variable	Measured as net income divided by total equity	Udoh et al. (2023)
Audit committee board size (ACS)	Independent variable	Measured total number of audit committee members	Shaker et al. (2023)
Audit committee board independence (AUCI)	Independent variable	percentage of non-executive directors to total number of directors	Abubakar et al. (2023)
Audit committee frequency of meeting (AUCM)	Independent variable	Total number of audit committee meetings per annum	Ugbah et al. (2023)
Audit committee financial expertise (AUCFE)	Independent variable	Percentage of audit committee members with accounting or financial education	Shaker et al. (2023)
Audit committee board gender diversity (AUCGD)	Independent variable	Percentage of the number of female directors on the audit committee.	Abubakar et al. (2023)

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics of the variables were carried out to show the nature and behaviour of the data using mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum. The analysis is presented in table 2:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	.4065492	7.000552	-.7806209	139.5148
ROE	2.18932	27.98186	-64.03081	382.2313
ACS	5.240786	.9856144	3	9
ACI	.0901229	.1453524	0	.67
ACM	3.511057	.9412551	1	6
ACFE	.8869779	.7859621	0	3
ABGD	.1215764	.1635485	0	.8
FSIZE	1.03	2.05	219871	1.20

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

Table 2 shows that the mean ROA is 40%, which implies that on average, manufacturing firms management in Nigeria are efficient in generating profits from their total assets. The dispersion which is measured as the standard deviation around the mean, stood at 700%. The minimum and maximum values of ROA are -78% and 13,951%, respectively. This finding implies that some manufacturing firms utilize larger assets to generate profits while others use less assets to generate their profits. On the other hand, the average ROE of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is 218.9% with a deviation of 2,798%. This implies that despite the high average value of ROE in the manufacturing sector, the variability or ability of the firms to generate profit from shareholders' funds is high.

The average audit committee board size of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is approximately 5, while the minimum and maximum are 3 and 98, respectively. The deviation from the average is approximately 1 board member. These findings imply that the committee's size is within the stipulated size of the SEC corporate governance codes. On the other hand, it is observed that the average number of independent non-executives on the audit committee is 9%.

The minimum number of independent directors in the audit committee is 0 and the maximum is 67%. The implication of this is that the average audit committee of manufacturing firms meets the stipulated code of corporate governance requirement of at least one independent director on the audit committee. The average frequency of audit committee meetings of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is 3.5 times per annum, with a deviation of 1. However, manufacturing firms minimum and maximum frequency of meetings are 1 and 6, respectively. In conclusion, it can be deduced that the average manufacturing firm meets the minimum requirement of 4 audit committee meetings per annum.

The audit committee is composed to provide monitoring oversight on the financial activities of the firm. It is therefore important that the audit committee is composed in such a manner that the committee members have the required financial expertise. From the findings, on average 88% of members of the committee possess an accounting or financial academic qualification. The minimum and maximum number of audit committee members with financial expertise is 0 and 3, respectively.

The finding implies that the committees is composed in such a manner as to provide adequate oversight function to the board. A descriptive analysis of manufacturing firms shows that the average gender diversity of the committee is 12%, while the minimum and maximum number of female directors on the audit committee is 0 and 80%, respectively. The deviation from the mean is 16%. The average firm size of manufacturing firms in Nigeria is 1.03 trillion Naira with a minimum and maximum value of 1.20 trillion Naira respectively. This indicated that the manufacturing sector is highly valuable.

Correlation Matrix

This section presents the pairwise correlation matrix which describes the relationship among the independent and dependent variables. The result of the test is presented in Table 2.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	ROA	ROE	ACS	ACI	ACM	ACFE	ABGD	FSIZE
ROA	1.0000							
ROE	0.4384	1.0000						
ACS	0.0413	0.0582	1.0000					
ACI	-0.0285	0.0345	-0.1350	1.0000				
ACM	0.0293	-0.0274	0.2445	-0.1066	1.0000			
ACFE	0.0726	-0.0323	0.1242	-0.0574	-0.1093	1.0000		
ABGD	-0.0377	-0.0777	-0.0178	0.2574	0.0416	-0.1147	1.0000	
FSIZE	-0.0144	0.1722	-0.0982	-0.0145	-0.0177	-0.0376	0.0501	1.0000

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

Table 3 shows the relationship between audit committee characteristics and the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The result shows that the relationship between ROA and audit committee size is positive. Implying an increase in the number of audit committees increases the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The result is similar when financial performance is proxied as ROE. Similarly, the relationship between audit committee meetings, audit committee financial expertise, and ROA is positively correlated. This implies that frequent meetings and the financial expertise of the board increase the ROA of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. In contrast, the relationship between audit committee independence, audit committee gender diversity, firm size, and ROA is negatively correlated, that is, increasing audit committee independence, audit committee gender diversity, and firm size results in a decrease in ROA. On the other hand, when financial performance is proxied with ROE, audit committee independence, and firm size are positively correlated. While audit committee meetings, audit committee financial expertise, and audit committee board gender diversity are negatively correlated with ROE. The conclusion made from these findings is that the outcome of the relationship between audit committee characteristics and financial performance is dependent on the proxy used in measuring financial performance.

Multicollinearity

Table 4: Multicollinearity test

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
ACS	1.17	0.853767
logfsize	1.15	0.868801
ACM	1.13	0.884039
ACI	1.10	0.911153
ABGD	1.08	0.926337
ACFE	1.05	0.948030
Mean VIF	1.11	

Source: Stata output (2024)

The regression analysis was subjected to a multicollinearity test to detect the presence of collinearity among the variables. The result shows that the mean of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was 1.11, which is much lower than the threshold of 10. The VIF for individual

variables was also very low. This indicates that the explanatory variables included in the model were not correlated, indicating an absence of multicollinearity between the variables.

Test of Hypotheses

The Hausman test was carried out to determine the fixed and random effects of the models. The result from the analysis is presented below:

Table 5: Hausman Test

Models	Chi ²	Probability
ROA	627.84	0.0000
ROE	62.40	0.0000

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

From Table 5, the result of the Hausman test favours the adoption of fixed effect panel regression in both models as shown by the probability value (P = 0.0000), which is significant at 5%.

Table 6: Test of hypotheses

Variables	ROA				ROE			
	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t
ACS	.0046337	.5357041	0.01	0.993	2.095923	1.932484	1.08	0.279
ACI	5.739651	3.887236	1.48	0.141	.1456345	14.0227	0.01	0.992
ACM	-.4152741	.6681541	-0.62	0.535	-4.150595	2.41028	-1.72	0.086
ACFE	1.378864	.6780879	2.03	0.043	-.132671	2.446115	-0.05	0.957
ABGD	-11.50975	3.189208	-3.61	0.000	-32.50547	11.50466	-2.83	0.005
LOGFSIZE	1.065077	1.052708	1.01	0.312	30.07485	3.797509	7.92	0.000
F statistics	2.99			0.007	11.11			0.000
R ² = 8.3%					R ² = 15.89%			

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

The analysis result in Table 6 shows the effect of audit committee characteristics on financial performance (proxy by ROA and ROE). The result shows that the coefficient of determination (R²) in model one (ROA) is 8.3% which explains that 8.3% of the variations in the ROA of listed manufacturing firms can be explained by audit committee characteristics (proxy as audit committee size, independence, frequency of meetings, financial expertise, gender diversity and firm size). However, the coefficient of determination is slightly higher when financial performance is proxied using ROE.

The variation stood at 15.89% which implies that the variation in ROE can be explained by audit committee characteristics (proxy as audit committee size, independence, frequency of meetings, financial expertise, gender diversity and firm size). The F statistics test was used to show the fitness of the model. The findings indicate that the F statistic of ROA and ROE are statistically significant at 5%. Thus, it can be inferred that the model is fit to explain the effect of audit committee characteristics on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

The panel fixed effect regression result shows that audit committee size has an insignificant positive effect on the ROA of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis which states that audit committee size has no significant effect on the ROA of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is accepted at 5% significance level ($P = 0.993$). Similarly, when financial performance is proxied using ROE, the result showed an insignificant positive effect of audit committee size on ROE ($P = 0.279$). Hence, it can be deduced that audit committee size does not affect the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This finding implies that the size of the audit committee does not affect the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This finding conforms to the study by Awad and Ghanem (2023), Itheyen (2021), and Meah et al. (2021) who showed that audit committee size has no significant contribution to firm performance. In contrast, Okeke (2021) and Okolie and Ogbaragu (2022) findings reveal that the audit committee size has a significant relationship with performance. Daniel et al. (2021) argued that the size of the audit committee determines the effectiveness and efficiency of the audit committee in carrying out its responsibilities. According to Ashari and Krismiaji (2020), a smaller audit committee is more effective in influencing performance since its members are more focused on talking about crucial financial reported concerns the company is facing. This view was supported by Tawfeeq and Alabdullah (2023) who found that the audit committee's size has a considerable detrimental impact on financial performance. According to the Resource Dependence Theory, however, larger audit committees may help companies perform better because they may use their varied range of skills and knowledge to enhance oversight and benefit shareholders and other stakeholders.

The fixed effect result from Table 5 shows that audit committee independence has a positive but insignificant effect on the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that audit committee independence has no significant effect on the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is accepted as indicated by the p-value ($P = 0.141$). In a similar vein, the result showed that the effect of audit committee independence on ROE is positive but insignificant at 5% significant level ($P = 0.992$). This study aligns with the findings of Abubakar et al. (2023), Awad and Ghanem (2023), Osevwe-Okoroyibo and Emeka-Nwokeji (2021) who found a negative but insignificant effect on the financial performance of firms. They argued that the independence of the audit committee to include independent directors does not necessarily translate to financial performance. In contrast, Bazhair (2022), Azam and Wang (2021) Mohamed and Bii (2018) Orjinta and Ikueze (2018) found a positive significant effect of audit committee composition on financial performance. Ali and Meah (2021) opined that more independent non-executive directors on corporate boards provide more independence to the audit committees. In contrast, Tawfeeq and Alabdullah (2023) found that the audit committee's independence has a considerable detrimental impact on financial performance. Namakavarani et al. (2021) argued that the composition of the audit board should be such that it promotes transparency in executing its duties. An audit committee comprising non-executive directors will properly conduct supervisory roles. The goal is to enable committee members to monitor the financial discretion of the management and ensure the credibility of the financial reports.

The result shows that audit committee's frequency of meetings has an insignificant negative effect on the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that audit committee frequency of meetings has no significant effect on the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is accepted as indicated by the p-value ($P = 0.535$) which is higher than 5% significance level. Findings also showed that when financial performance is proxied as ROE, the result is insignificant and negative at 5% significant level ($P = 0.086$). This finding implies that increasing the number of meetings by the audit committee does not translate into financial performance in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. On the contrary, Fariha et al. (2021), Osevwe-Okoroyibo and Emeka-Nwokeji (2021), Okeke (2021) and Mwangi (2023) found that audit meeting has a positive and significant relationship with ROA.

Al-Jalahma (2022) opined that the audit committee meetings measure their effectiveness and are considered an essential element of reviewing the financial reporting process of the firm. According to Musa et al. (2017), the audit committee meetings show how serious the committee is and allows the committee to engage external auditors who can improve the report's credibility and establish confidence in the shareholders. In contrast, studies such as Awad and Ghanem (2023), Al-Jalahma (2022) Hamada and Jwailes (2021) Okolie and Ogbaragu (2022), and Tawfeeq and Alabdullah (2023) found that the frequency of meetings does not result to financial performance. This study contradicts the agency theory which suggests that audit committee meetings play a vital role in aligning the interests of shareholders and management, enhancing monitoring and control, promoting accountability and incentives, providing expertise and advice, and facilitating communication and transparency. On the contrary, fulfilling these functions, audit committee meetings can positively influence the financial performance of firms, leading to improved outcomes and increased shareholder value.

The null hypothesis which states that audit committee financial expertise has no significant effect on the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria is rejected as shown by a significant level ($P = 0.043$). Hence, the findings indicate that the audit committee frequency of meetings positively affects the ROA of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This finding implies that an increase in the number of audit committee members with financial expertise increases ROA by 137.8%. On the other hand, when financial performance is proxied using ROE, the result is negative but insignificant as indicated by the p value ($P = 0.957$). Hence, audit committee financial expertise does not affect ROE of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

This finding was corroborated by the studies of Mohamed and Bii (2018), Bazhair (2022), Azam and Wang (2021) and Okolie and Ogbaragu (2022) found that financial expertise is a vital skillset requirement for audit committee members. They argued that a highly competent audit committee brings specialized knowledge and skills to the table. Members with financial expertise, accounting qualifications, and industry-specific experience are better equipped to understand complex financial transactions and potential risks. This expertise enables them to provide valuable insights and advice to management, enhancing the quality of financial reporting and decision-making. Consequently, organizations with audit committees comprising experienced professionals tend to have more accurate financial statements, reducing the

likelihood of material misstatements or fraudulent activities. In addition, the presence of knowledgeable audit committee members instills investor confidence. External stakeholders, including shareholders and creditors, rely on the integrity of financial information when making investment decisions. A competent audit committee acts as a safeguard against financial mismanagement and provides assurance that the organization's financial statements are reliable. This increased confidence can lead to a lower cost of capital, improved access to funding, and enhanced shareholder value. In contrast, using ROE as a financial performance proxy, the result was insignificant. This aligns with the study of Awad and Ghanem (2023), Mawardi et al. (2023), Osevwé-Okoroyibo and Emeka-Nwokeji (2021) and Olayinka (2019) who found that the financial expertise of audit committee members does not influence the financial performance of firms.

Table 6 shows the result of the audit committee's gender diversity and return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on the analysis, the findings reveal that audit committee gender diversity has a significant negative effect on the return on assets of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 5% significance level ($P = 0.000$). Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This finding implies that a unit increase in female directors on the audit board results in a decrease in ROA by 1,150% in ROA. Similarly, when financial performance is proxied using ROE, the result showed that audit committee gender diversity is significant by negative at 5% significant level ($P = 0.005$). In a similar vein, Musah et al. (2022) found that gender diversity in audit committees have a negative effect on financial performance while Suherman et al. (2021), Awotomilusi and Dare (2022) and Ugbah et al. (2023) claimed that audit committees increasing the number of female representatives in the audit committee does not affect the financial performance of firms.

Prior studies such as Abubakar et al. (2023), Juwita (2023), Shukla et al. (2021), Dwalikat et al. (2021), Onyekwere and Babangida (2022) and Kabara et al. (2022) found a positive significant effect. This finding implies that firstly, gender diversity brings a broader range of perspectives and experiences to the decision-making process. This diversity of thought can lead to more robust discussions and a more comprehensive evaluation of financial risks and opportunities. Different viewpoints and approaches can help identify potential biases and enhance critical thinking, ultimately leading to improved decision-making and financial outcomes. Secondly, gender diversity fosters greater independence and accountability within audit committees. Research suggests that diverse boards tend to exhibit higher levels of objectivity and are less prone to groupthink.

Female board members, in particular, are more likely to challenge the status quo and ask tough questions, leading to a more rigorous examination of financial information and controls. This increased scrutiny can help identify potential errors, fraud, or unethical practices, thereby improving the overall quality of financial reporting and reducing the likelihood of financial misstatements. Furthermore, gender diversity within audit committees can positively influence investor perception and trust. In an increasingly socially conscious business environment, stakeholders value diversity and inclusion. Organizations that demonstrate a commitment to gender diversity are often seen as progressive and forward-thinking.

This perception can enhance the organization's reputation, attract socially responsible investors, and potentially lead to improved access to capital. The inclusion of both male and female members fosters diverse perspectives, improves decision-making, enhances independence, and promotes investor trust. By embracing gender diversity, organizations can tap into a wider pool of talent, perspectives, and experiences, ultimately driving better financial outcomes.

The control variable proxy as firm size showed a positive insignificant effect in the ROA model. Implying that firm size does not control the effect of audit committee characteristics on ROA. However, the result is different when financial performance is proxied using ROE. Findings showed that firm size is significant and positive, implying that firm size positively influences the effect of audit committee characteristics on ROE in manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Robustness Tests

They are conditions that need to be fulfilled in carrying out regression analysis. This is important to avoid spurious regression. These tests include multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity tests. Below are the outcomes of the findings.

Heteroscedasticity

Table 7: Breusch-Pagan/cook-Weisberg test for Heteroscedasticity

Model	Chi ²	Probability
ROA	627.84	0.0000
ROE	832.64	0.0000

Source: Authors compilation (2024)

One of the statistical assumptions of regression analysis is that the error terms for all observations have a common variance (homoscedastic). On the contrary, varying variance errors are said to be heteroscedastic. The heteroskedasticity was tested in the residuals of the estimations using the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test. The null hypothesis is stated thus, there is no heteroskedasticity. From the analysis in Table 7, the model has heteroskedasticity. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected because it was found to be significant at 5%, which led to the estimation of both fixed and random effects.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study examined the effect of audit committee characteristics (proxy as audit committee size, audit committee composition, audit committee meetings, audit committee frequency of meeting, audit committee financial expertise, and audit committee gender diversity) on the financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The summary of the findings is as follows: Audit committee size has an insignificant positive effect on the financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee independence has an insignificant positive effect on the financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee frequency of

meetings has an insignificant negative effect on the financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee financial expertise has a significant positive effect on ROA. In contrast, the result is insignificant and negative on the ROE of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Audit committee gender diversity has a significant negative effect on the financial performance (ROA and ROE) of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that

- i. The study found an insignificant effect of audit committee size on financial performance. It is therefore recommended that manufacturing firms in Nigeria should aim for an audit committee size that is large enough to provide diverse perspectives but small enough to maintain efficiency and effective communication. Generally, 3 to 5 members is considered optimal for many firms.
- ii. The study found an insignificant effect of audit committee independence on financial performance. It is recommended that manufacturing firms should ensure that the majority of the audit committee members are independent of management to enhance objectivity and reduce potential conflicts of interest. In addition, firms should appoint an independent chair for the audit committee to further strengthen its oversight role.
- iii. It is recommended that the frequency of audit committee meetings may not significantly impact financial performance. Management of manufacturing firms should ensure that audit committee meetings have focused agendas that prioritize critical financial oversight issues. Avoid overloading meetings with routine or administrative matters that can be handled elsewhere.

References

- 1) Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of Nigeria listed deposit money banks. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.
- 2) Al-Jalahma, A. (2022). Impact of audit committee characteristics on firm performance: Evidence from Bahrain. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 20(1), 247-261. doi:10.21511/ppm.20(1).2022.21
- 3) Ali, M. H. & Meah, M. R. (2021) Factors of audit committee independence: An empirical study from an emerging economy, *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1), 1-23 DOI: 10.1080/23311975.2021.1888678
- 4) Arens, A.A., Elder, R.J., & Beasley, M.S. (2009). *Auditing and assurance services: An integrated approach*, 13th Edition, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- 5) Ashari, S. & Krismiaji, K. (2019). Audit committee characteristics and financial performance: Indonesian evidence. *Equity*, 22(2), 139-152. doi.org/10.34209/equ.v22i2.1326
- 6) Awad, G., & Ghanem, M. G. (2023). Board of Directors, Audit Committee and Firms' Performance. *Dutch Journal of Finance and Management*, 6(1), 20594. https://doi.org/10.55267/djfm/13463
- 7) Awotomilusi, N. S. & Dare, C. T. (2022). Gender diversity and firm value of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria, *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 10(4), 828-837. DOI: 10.13189/ujaf.2022.100405
- 8) Azam, M. & Wang, M. (2021). The effects of the audit committee independence and expertise on firms' value, an empirical study on Palestine empirical study on Palestine, *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 7(1), 14-20. DOI: https://doi.org/10.32861/ijefr.71.14.20

- 9) Bazhair, A. H. (2022). Audit committee attributes and financial performance of Saudi non-financial listed firms, *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10:1, 2127238, DOI: 10.1080/23322039.2022.2127238
- 10) Daniel, N., Eguasa, B. E. & Excellence, B. (2021). Audit committee and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria, *International Journal of Research, and Innovation in Social Science*, 5(12), 307-313
- 11) Dwaikat, N., Qubbaj, I. S., & Queiri, A. (2021). Gender diversity on the board of directors and its impact on the Palestinian financial performance of the firm, *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 9, 1-15. doi: 10.1080/23322039.2021.1948659.
- 12) El'Hawary, E. (2021). Audit committee effectiveness and company performance: Evidence from Egypt. *Journal of Governance & Regulation*, 10(2), 134–156. <https://doi.org/10.22495/jgrv10i2art12>
- 13) Fariha, R., Hossain, M. & Ghosh, R. (2021). Board characteristics, audit committee attributes and firm performance: empirical evidence from emerging economy, *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 7(1), 84-96. DOI 10.1108/AJAR-11-2020-0115
- 14) Hamada, R. & Jwailles, A. R. (2021). The effect of audit committee characteristics (committee size, committee independence, committee gender diversity, committee frequency of meetings on Jordanian firm performance TQ, *Journal of Business Management*, 7(10), 14-32
- 15) Iheyen, C. (2021). Audit committee attributes and the value of firm: evidence from listed insurance companies in Nigeria, *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Accounting*, 2(1), 21-35. Available at <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/jocia>
- 16) Kabara, A. S., Khatib, S. F. Bazhair, A. H. & Sulimany, H. G. (2022). The effect of the Board's educational and gender diversity on the firms' performance: Evidence from non-financial firms in developing country. *Sustainability*, 14, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141711058>
- 17) Maina, L. K., & Oluoch, O. (2018). Effect of corporate audit committee characteristics on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Information Technology*, 4(10), 684-701
- 18) Mawardi, W., Harjum, M. & Mulyo, H. (2023). The Role of Audit Committee Characteristics and I.C. Performance on I.C. Disclosure: Evidence from the Indonesian banking sector. *Economies* 11(7), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies11010007>
- 19) Mohamed, A. I. & Bii, P. K. (2018). Role of audit committee financial expertise on financial performance of banking and insurance firms in Nairobi securities exchange, *International Journal of Academics & Research*, 1(1), 302-305
- 20) Musah, A. Padi, A. & Okyere, B. (2022). Corporate governance, gender diversity, audit committee characteristics and audit fees in Ghana, *Academy of Accounting and Financial Studies Journal*, 26(2), 1-17
- 21) Ojeka, S. A., Iyoha, F. O., & Obigbemi, I. F. (2013). Audit committee characteristics and firm financial performance in Nigeria. *International Business Information Management Association Conference, Rome, Italy*
- 22) Okeke, P. C. (2021). Audit committee attributes and corporate performance: evidence from selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 9(9), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ejaaf.2013>
- 23) Okolie, A. O. & Ogaragu, J. S. (2022). Audit committee effectiveness and corporate financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria, *International Journal of Economics and Management Studies*, 9(3), 24-34. <https://doi.org/10.14445/23939125/IJEMS-V9I3P104>

- 24) Orjinta, H. I., & Ikueze, N. E. (2018). Effect of audit committee characteristics on performance of non-financial firms: Evidence from a recessed economy. *International Journal of Innovation and Applied Studies*, 24(1), 289–298
- 25) Osewwe-Okoroyibo, E. E. & Emeka-Nwokeji, N. A. (2021). Examining effect of audit committee attributes on firm performance: evidence from listed food and beverages firms in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 9(8), 26-43. <https://doi.org/10.37745/ejaifr.2013>
- 26) Rahel T. Z. & Serkalem T. B. (2010). The Impact of Board Composition on Accounting Profitability of the Firm: A Study of Large Capas in Sweden, *A Master Thesis of Umea School of Business*, Retrieved from <http://www.fpssc.ca/files/FPSC%20Board%20competency%20profile.pdf>
- 27) Shukla, A., Sivasavkaran, N., Singh, P., Kanagaraj, A., & Chakraborty, S. (2021). Do women directors impact the risk and return of Indian banks? *IIM Kozhikode Society & Management Review*, 10(1), 44–65.
- 28) Suherman, L., Rmadhania, M., Ahmad, G. N., Zakaria, A., & WEitastuti, R. S. (2021). The effect of gender diversity and the business expertise of female directors on firm performance: Evidence from the Indonesia Stock Exchange, *International Journal of Business*, 26(3), 43-50.
- 29) Tawfeeq, T. & Alabdullah, Y. (2023). The role of audit committees in Omani business context: do they affect the performance of non-financial companies, *Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Business*, 2(4), 643-659
- 30) Udoh E.S., Ikpe I.J., and Emenyi E.O. (2023) Board Committees' Independence and Financial Performance of Listed Non-Finance Firms in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 11(7), 47-76. doi: <https://doi.org/10.37745/ejaifr.2013/vol11n74776>
- 31) Udoh E.S., Ikpe I.J., and Emenyi E.O. (2023) Board Committees' Independence and Financial Performance of Listed Non-Finance Firms in Nigeria, *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 11(7), 47-76. doi: <https://doi.org/10.37745/ejaifr.2013/vol11n74776>
- 32) Ugbah, A. A., Amahi, F.U. & Offor, N. T. (2023). Audit committee composition and tax planning in Nigeria, *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 23(21), 62-70. DOI: 10.9734/AJEBA/2023/v23i211116
- 33) Wobo, H. O. & Ibanichuka, E. A. (2021). Effect of audit committee on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 9(1), 669-675